

Suitability Evaluation and Mapping of Soils of University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, for Cowpea Production

Onyechere, A.U^{1*}, Onyechere I. C²., Ukabiala, M. E¹., Amanze C. T¹., Okerefor D. O¹., Ibe O. K¹.

¹Department of Soil Science, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria.

²Department of Civil Engineering, Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author: onyechere.adaobi@gmail.com

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Abstract: This study assessed the suitability of soils at the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences (UAES), Umuagwo, Southeastern Nigeria, for cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*) cultivation. Using FAO guidelines and parametric evaluation methods, ten soil mapping units (P1 P10) were analysed based on climate, topography, wetness, physical properties, and fertility characteristics. Field sampling and laboratory analyses were conducted to determine critical soil attributes which include texture, pH, organic carbon, cation exchange capacity (CEC), base saturation, and available phosphorus. Suitability classes were derived using established thresholds adapted to cowpea requirements. The results indicated that climatic, topographic, and wetness conditions were highly suitable (S1) across all sites. Soil texture and structure were generally favourable, though sand dominance in a few locations (P8, P9 and P10) posed physical limitations. The major constraints to productivity were fertility-related, particularly low organic carbon (<1.0%), suboptimal CEC, and acidic pH (<5.5). Consequently, actual suitability ranged from marginally suitable (S3) to currently not suitable (N1), while potential suitability improved to highly suitable (S1) under fertility management practices. The actual suitability map revealed that greater percentage of the study areas showed marginally suitable for cowpea production due to fertility constraint with areas towards the Otammiri river showing temporally not suitable (N1) for cowpea production due to both fertility and soil physical characteristics constraint. However, the potential suitability map displayed the impact of corrective soil management practices improving most of the soil study area to Highly Suitable (S1) soil for cowpea production.

Keywords: cowpea, land suitability, crop production, fertility constraint

Introduction

Agricultural production in Nigeria, particularly in the southeastern region, has historically been focused on staple crops such as cassava, yam, and maize (Asadu et

al., 2016) . These crops have not only served as the dietary backbone of the region but have also played a vital role in rural livelihoods and local economies (Chiaka et al., 2022). However, in recent years, an

observable transition has emerged in farming patterns across several communities, especially in the southeastern Nigeria, where there is a trending shift toward the cultivation of fast growing crops capable of surviving in marginal soils(Onyenekwe et al., 2024). This change is influenced by multiple interrelated factors, including declining soil fertility due to overcultivation, conditions due to climate change, market demand dynamics, shorter cropping cycles, and the need for more resilient and economically viable crop options.

Cowpea, a leguminous crop known for its high protein content, nitrogen-fixing ability, and adaptability to marginal soils, has increasingly gained attention among farmers (Chiaka et al., 2022). Its short growth cycle allows for multiple harvests within a year, offering quicker returns to farmers compared to crops like cassava and yam that require longer periods to mature. Additionally, cowpea is highly adaptable to drought-prone and marginal environments, making it a more resilient option in the face of climate change (Igomu & Idoga, 2017). cowpea production will not only guide optimal land use within the university but also offer broader benefits to the host community (Obasi, et al., 2017).These include opportunities for farmer training and demonstration plots, improved food

Given these benefits, cowpea production is increasingly being viewed not only as a sustainable farming choice but also as a pathway to improved food security and economic stability in regions like Umuagwo.

Soil suitability evaluation is a critical step in achieving sustainable agricultural production, particularly in regions where land resources must be optimized to support food security and economic development (Chiaka et al., 2024). In southeastern Nigeria, the need to diversify crop production in response to soil degradation, climate variability, and market shifts has become increasingly urgent. The University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences (UAES), Umuagwo, located in Ohaji/Egbema Local Government Area of Imo State, presents a unique opportunity for such evaluation due to its strategic location, fertile land base, and role as a center for agricultural education and innovation.

This study focuses on the suitability classification of the soils within UAES for cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*) production. Assessing the suitability of UAES soils for security, creation of employment, and increased access to research-based agricultural practices. By identifying the most favourable soil types and conditions for cowpea cultivation, this research aims to support and informed decision-making

for both academic and local agricultural stakeholders, ultimately promoting inclusive and sustainable rural development in the villages around the school.

Materials and Methods

The study area description

The cowpea suitability study was conducted within the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences (UAES), Umuagwo. The area lies between latitude 5° 19' 05" N and 5° 20' 10" N and longitude 6° 57' 0" and 6° 58' 05" as shown in Figure 1. The University has a land area of about 3km² and over 300 hectares of land. The area belong to the low lying part

Field work

Ten representative soil mapping units (P001 to P010) were delineated based on landform, vegetation cover, and apparent soil variability (Adamu et al., 2017). Auger samples were collected from the depth of 0 -15cm, 15 - 30cm, 30 - 60cm and 60 - 90cm using a Dutch auger

of southeastern Nigeria and soils are derived from coastal plain sand (Obasi, et al., 2017). The University is also bounded by the east by the Otammiri River, a major hydrological feature in Imo State (Fig 1). The region has a humid tropical climate and the rainforest vegetations have been drastically altered with arable crop production. The area experiences average daily minimum temperature range of about 19 - 24°C and maximum mean range of about 28 - 35°C (Ogbuagu & Okoli 2013). The mean relative humidity is up to 80% and a long wet season that starts from April and ends in November. The total mean annual rainfall is greater than 2000mm (Obasi, et al., 2017). (Okorie et al., 2020). Each site was georeferenced using a GPS and the coordinates recorded as shown in Table 1 for geospatial analysis. The field observations also included slope measurements, drainage condition, evidence of flooding, and soil depth estimation.

Figure 1 Location map of the study area.

Soil analysis

Soil samples were dried in air, ground, and passed through a 2mm sieve for analysis. Standard methods were followed for laboratory procedures: soil texture was assessed using the hydrometer method, pH was determined in a 1:2.5 soil-water mixture with a pH meter, and organic carbon was estimated using the Walkley Black wet oxidation technique, the cation exchangeable capacity (CEC) was assessed using the ammonium acetate method at a pH of 7. Base saturation was derived from the exchangeable bases and

CEC. Available phosphorus was evaluated through the Bray-1 extraction technique, while calcium content was determined with atomic absorption spectrophotometry (Okorie et al., 2020; Trigunasih et al., 2023).

Land suitability evaluation

The suitability of the soil was classified following FAO land evaluation framework (FOA, 2025). The land use requirement thresholds specific to cowpea production is presented in Table 2. This was adopted for placing the land unit into the appropriate suitability classes (Igomu & Idoga, 2017).

Table 1 Coordinates of the sampling points in decimal degrees

Locations	Latitude (N)	Longitude (E)
P1	5.334463	6.950047
P2	5.329516	6.953502
P3	5.325788	6.954457
P4	5.321431	6.95564
P5	5.334	6.959
P6	5.329543	6.959455
P7	5.325	6.961
P8	5.328075	6.966213
P9	5.329	6.965
P10	5.332743	6.963992

The limiting factors of each mapping unit was rated in percentage and the index of suitability of each profile was computed using the equation:

$$IP = A \times \sqrt{\frac{B}{100} \times \frac{C}{100} \times \frac{D}{100} \times \frac{E}{100}} \quad (1)$$

S2 (moderately suitable), S3 (marginally suitable), N1 (currently not suitable) and N2 (potentially not suitable) which are equivalent to index of productivity value of 100-75, 74-50, 49-25, 24-15, 14-0 respectively. Actual Suitability was based on unamended field and laboratory conditions. Potential Suitability was projected by adjusting parameters such as

where: IP = Index of Productivity

A = Overall lowest characteristic

B, C, D, F = The lowest characteristic ratings for each land quality group.

The aggregate suitability scores were placed on suitability classes S1 (highly suitable), pH, organic matter, and available phosphorus to ideal values under improved management. Limiting factors were identified using the most limiting approach (Igomu & Idoga, 2017; Obasi, et al., 2017). The aggregate suitability scores for the actual and potential suitability were encoded in GIS software (Arc GIS 10.7) for the production of thematic maps.

Table 2 Land specifications for different suitability classes for cowpea Production

Land qualities	Suitability classes					
	S1 ₁ (85-95%)	S1 ₂ (60-85%)	S ₂ (40-60%)	S ₃ (25-40%)	N ₁ (25-40%)	N ₂ (0-25%)
Climate (c)						
Annual rainfall (mm)	>1200	1000-1200	800-1000	600-800	-	>600
Length of rainy season (months)	>5	4-5	3-4	2-3	-	>2
Mean annual maximum temp. (°C)	>29	27-29	24-27	22-24	-	>22
Average daily minimum temp. (°C)	>20	18-20	16-18	14-16	-	>14
Mean annual temp. (°C)	>25	22-25	20-22	18-20	-	>18
Relative humidity (%)	>75	70-75	65-70	60-65	-	>60
Topography (t)						
Slope (%)	0-4	4-8	8-12	12-16	>16	-
Wetness (w)						
Flooding	F ₀	F ₀	F ₁	F ₂	-	F ₃
Drainage	Well drained	Well drained	Well drained	Imperfect	Poor	V. Poor
Soil physical properties (s)						
Texture	LS	SL	SC	SCL	Any	C, CL
Structure	Crumb	Crumb	S.a blocky	S.a blocky	Columnar	
Coarse fragments (vol. %) 0-30 cm	3-10	10-15	15-35	35-55	-	>55
Depth (cm)	>100	90-100	50-90	25-50	-	>25
Fertility (f)						
Cation exchange capacity (cmol/kg)	>10	8-10	6-8	4-6	2-4	<2.0
Base saturation	>70	60-70	40-60	20-40	-	0
pH	>6.0-6.5	6.0-7.0	5.5-6.0	5.0-5.5	4.5-5.0	<4.5
Organic carbon (%) 0-30 cm	>1.5-2.0	1.5-2.0	1.25-1.5	1.0-1.25	< 1.0	<1.0
Ca (mole fraction)	0.8-0.9	0.7-0.8	0.6-0.7	0.4-0.6	0.2-0.4	<0.2
Avail. P (mg/kg) 0-30 cm	>20	16-20	12-16	8-12	4.8	<4.0
Salinity and alkalinity (dS/m) (n)						
	<1	1-2	2-3	3-4	4-8	>8

(Igomu & Idoga, 2017).

Results and Discussion

The land suitability evaluation conducted for cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata*) production at the University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences (UAES), Umuagwo is presented in Table 4. The result reveals important insights into the agroecological potential of the area. The

classification utilized the framework of the FAO land evaluation guidelines (FOA, 2025) and adapted criteria based on cowpea-specific land requirements (Table 2). Table 3 reveals the land qualities/characteristics of Soils Of UAES, Umuagwo for Cowpea Production and assessment accounted for climatic,

topographic, wetness, physical, and fertility-related soil qualities across ten mapped units (P001 P010).

Climatic parameters across the study area fall within the S1 (highly suitable) class for cowpea cultivation. Annual rainfall consistently exceeded 2000 mm, well above the minimum threshold of 1200 mm for S1

classification. Similarly, the length of the rainy season (8 months), mean annual temperature (25.9°C), maximum temperatures (28 35°C), and minimum daily temperatures (19 24°C) all favour cowpea growth and development. Relative humidity values (75 80%) also align with optimal requirements (75% and above).

Figure 2 The actual suitability map of UAES for cowpea production

Figure 3 The potential suitability map of UAES for cowpea production

Table 3 Land qualities/characteristics of soils of UAES, Umuagwo for cowpea production

Land qualities	P001	P002	P003	P004	P005	P006	P007	P008	P009	P010
Fertility (f)										
Cation exchange capacity (cmol/kg)	6.3	6.2	6.7	5.4	5.4	5.8	5.7	5.3	5.3	5.2
Base saturation	89.1	84.4	86.5	86.2	86.1	76.3	76.2	81.1	82.1	83.3
pH	5.3	5.3	4.9	5.6	5.7	5.0	5.1	5.2	5.1	4.9
Organic carbon (%) 0-30 cm	0.7	0.9	0.7	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.4
Ca (mole fraction)	3.24	2.3	2.7	2.0	2.1	2.2	2.2	2.0	2.0	2.1
Avail. P (mg/kg) 0-30 cm	19.1	20.4	18.8	14.6	14.3	15.1	14.9	13.1	14.2	15.6
Wetness (w)										
Flooding	F0									
Drainage	WD									
Climate (c)										
Annual rainfall (mm)	>2000	>2000	>2000	>2000	>2000	>2000	>2000	>2000	>2000	>2000
Length of rainy season (months)	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Mean annual maximum temp. (°C)	28 - 35	28 - 35	28 - 35	28 - 35	28 - 35	28 - 35	28 - 35	28 - 35	28 - 35	28 - 35
Average daily minimum temp. (°C)	19 - 24	19 - 24	19 - 24	19 - 24	19 - 24	19 - 24	19 - 24	19 - 24	19 - 24	19 - 24
Mean annual temp. (°C)	25.9	25.9	25.9	25.9	25.9	25.9	25.9	25.9	25.9	25.9
Relative humidity (%)	75-80	75-80	75-80	75-80	75-80	75-80	75-80	75-80	75-80	75-80
Soil physical properties (s)										
Texture	LS	Sand	Sand	Sand						
Structure	crumb									
Coarse fragments (vol. %) 0-30 cm	3-10	3-10	3-10	3-10	3-10	3-10	3-10	3-10	3-10	3-10
Depth (cm)	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100	>100
Topography (t)										
Slope (%)	0-4	0-4	0-4	0-4	0-4	0-4	0-4	0-4	0-4	0-4

Table 4 Suitability class scores of soils of uaes, Umuagwo for cowpea production

Land qualities	P001	P002	P003	P004	P005	P006	P007	P008	P009	P010
Fertility (f)										
Cation exchange capacity (cmol/kg)	S2 (50)	S2 (50)	S2 (50)	S3(40)	S3(40)	S3(40)	S3(40)	S3(40)	S3(40)	S3(40)
Base saturation	S1 (100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)							
pH	S3 (40)	S3 (40)	S3(40)	S2(60)	S2(60)	S3 (40)	S3 (40)	S3 (40)	S3 (40)	S3(40)
Organic carbon (%) 0-30 cm	N1(30)	N1(40)	N1(40)	N1(30)	N1 (30)	S3(40)	S3(40)	S3(40)	S3(40)	N1(30)
Ca (mole fraction)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)							
Avail. P (mg/kg) 0-30 cm	S1 (85)	S1 (100)	S1 (85)	S2(60)	S2(60)	S2(60)	S2(60)	S2(60)	S2(60)	S2(60)
Wetness (w)										
Flooding	S1 (100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)							
Drainage	S1 (100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)							
Climate (c)										
Annual rainfall (mm)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)							
Length of rainy season (months)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)							
Mean annual maximum temp. (°C)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)							
Average daily minimum temp. (°C)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)							
Mean annual temp. (°C)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)							
Relative humidity (%)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)							
Soil physical properties (s)										
Texture	S1 (100)	N1 (40)	N1 (40)	N1 (40)						
Structure	S1 (100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)							
Coarse fragments (vol. %) 0-30 cm	S1 (100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)							
Depth (cm)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)							
Topography (t)										
Slope (%)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)							
Aggregate Suitability										
Actual Suitability	S3(30)f	S3(40)f	S3(40)f	S3(30)f	S3(30)f	S3(40)f	S3(40)f	S3(25.3)fs	S3(25.3)fs	N1(18.97)fs
Potential Suitability	S1(100)	S3(40)	S3(40)s	S3(40)s						

Aggregate suitability scores: S1=100-75, S2=74-50, S3=49-25, N1=24-15, N2=14-0

f = fertility limitation, s = soil characteristics limitation

These findings are consistent with studies by the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (Singh et al., 1997) who emphasized that cowpea thrives in warm climates with annual rainfall between 600 mm and 1200 mm, though higher rainfall with proper drainage does not pose a constraint. Thus, the climate in UAES poses no limiting factor, providing a favourable baseline for rainfed cowpea production. This result is noteworthy for strategic crop planning under climate-smart agriculture in southeastern Nigeria (Idumah et al., 2016).

Topographic and wetness characteristics across all profiles were uniformly rated S1. Slopes ranged from 0-4%, minimizing erosion risk and allowing efficient field operations. The absence of flooding (F0) and the presence of well-drained soils further reinforced suitability. These observations are supported by Mac Carthy et al., (2018) who identified slope and drainage as critical physical parameters for legume crop performance in humid tropics. Well-drained soils minimize root rot and promote aerobic conditions essential for root nodulation and nitrogen fixation by cowpea.

Soil texture across most sites was loamy sand (LS) or sand, with crumb structure, minimal coarse fragments (3-10%), and depths exceeding 100 cm all contributing

to high water infiltration and deep rooting potential. These attributes qualified seven of the ten locations (P1-P7) as S1 in soil physical property criteria. However, sandy textures in P8, P9 and P10 lowered their suitability to N1 (currently not suitable) due to poor water and nutrient retention associated with sandy soils (Onweremadu et al., 2024). Coarser textures increase drought susceptibility and leaching losses, making texture a moderate limitation in certain plots.

Despite favourable climate and physical conditions, soil fertility emerged as the primary limiting factor in actual land suitability. Cation exchange capacity (CEC) ranged between 5.2 and 6.7 cmol/kg, placing many sites in the moderate (S2) and marginal (S3) suitability class. This reflects low nutrient-holding capacity, especially concerning exchangeable bases essential for cowpea nutrition (Igomu & Idoga, 2017). Soil pH values (4.9-5.7) suggest moderate acidity, while some locations (P4 and P5) met moderate suitability (S2) thresholds of pH 5.5-6.0, others fell into marginal suitability score, indicating pH levels below 5.0, a critical constraint to nutrient availability and rhizobial activity (Onweremadu et al., 2024).

Organic carbon content was critically low across all sites, ranging from 0.4-0.9%, thereby categorizing all profiles to range

from marginal suitable (S3) to currently not suitable (N1) for cowpea production. This deficiency undermines soil biological activity, moisture retention, and overall soil structure. According to Adesodun & Adekonoj (2011), organic carbon levels below 1.0% limit microbial processes and reduce legume yield potential. Available phosphorus levels ranged from 13.1 to 20.4 mg/kg; though generally moderate (S2), these are insufficient in the absence of fertilization, particularly given the crop's phosphorus demand during flowering and pod filling.

Consequently, the aggregate suitability ratings show that all mapping units fall within the S3 class (marginally suitable), with the exception of P10, which was rated N1 (currently not suitable). The main limiting factors were soil fertility and texture, as indicated by the suffixes "f" and "s" respectively in Table 4. If fertility enhancement measures such as liming, organic amendments, and phosphorus supplementation are applied, all sites except P8 P10 could reach S1 potential suitability. Units P8 P10, even with fertility improvements, remain constrained by soil texture, thus improving only to S3 potential.

The Suitability Map

The actual suitability map as represented in Figure 2 shows two dominant suitability classes; marginally suitable (S3)f and not suitable (N1)fs. Greater percentage of the study areas showed marginally suitable for cowpea production due to fertility constraint with areas towards the Otammiri river showing temporally not suitable (N1) for cowpea production due to both fertility and soil physical characteristics constraint. This pattern reflects the prevalence of soil fertility limitations (f), such as low organic carbon (<1.0%), acidic pH (<5.5), and low phosphorus availability, across all sites and then additionally soil physical limitation (s) in the eastern zones stems from coarse-textured sandy soils with poor water-holding capacity. The red zone adjacent to Otamiri River suggests possible alluvial sand deposits with excessively drained or leached soils, leading to very low nutrient retention. The central and western zones, while still constrained, offer more favourable physical conditions (loamy sands, good depth, and structure) for cowpea production.

The potential suitability map as represented in Figure 3 highlights the impact of corrective soil management practices. The dark green area, representing Highly Suitable (S1) land, now dominates the central and western part of the

University. A light green band, indicating Moderately Suitable (S2)s, covers a transition zone where fertility constraints may be correctable, but physical texture remains a limiting factor.

The brown zone, still Marginally Suitable (S3)s, remains in the far eastern edge, where poor texture limits productivity even after fertility improvement. This improvement demonstrates the potential of organic matter enrichment, phosphorus fertilization, and liming to restore cowpea suitability across most of the area. The delineation of improved zones offers valuable guidance for soil-specific interventions, rather than generalized land use decisions.

Conclusion

The results of this study indicate that although climatic and physical land characteristics in UAES, Umuagwo are

generally optimal for cowpea cultivation, soil fertility limitations especially low organic carbon, acidic pH, and suboptimal phosphorus availability constrain actual productivity. By implementing soil management strategies, particularly organic matter enhancement, acidity correction, and phosphorus enrichment, the productivity of cowpea in UAES, Umuagwo can be significantly improved. These interventions are not only agronomically sound but also environmentally sustainable, offering long-term benefits for food security and soil health in Southeastern Nigeria.

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